

Synthesis of Sulfide Perovskites by Sulfurization with Boron Sulfides

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1. Materials

The starting materials were BaZrO₃ (99%, Alfa Aesar), SrZrO₃ (99.3%, Alfa Aesar), Eu₂O₃ (99.99%), ZrO₂ (Pure, Soviet Union), BaCO₃ (pure, Lachema), SrCO₃ (99.9%, Sigma Aldrich), HfO₂ (99.95% Alfa Aesar), SrO (99.9%, Sigma Aldrich), Ba (99.9%, Alfa Aesar), Sr (99.8%, Alfa Aesar), S (99.98% Sigma Aldrich), B (98% Alfa Aesar), BaS (99.7%, Alfa Aesar), SrS (99%, Strem Chemicals), ZrS₂ (99%, Strem Chemicals).

2. Syntheses details

In a typical reaction, the starting materials (ternary oxide, binary oxides, element and binary oxide, carbonate) were ground with boron and sulfur in an agate mortar for 10-15 min. Well ground powder was transferred to a 15 mm i.d. quartz tube. The tube was connected to a Schlenk line and evacuated at <2 Pa

for 30 min while the bottom part of the tube with the reaction mixture was immersed in water bath heated to 70 °C to remove any residual moisture from the tube and the sample. The tube was then flame sealed under vacuum. The typical length of the sealed ampule was ~13 cm. During the flame sealing, the part of the tube containing the reagents powder mixture was immersed in cold water bath to prevent the reaction mixture heating from the sealing torch. The sealed reaction ampule with the reagents was transferred into a temperature calibrated furnace where it was heated at temperatures 500-1100 °C. The typical heating ramp rate was 5 °C/min with the holding time 5 hrs. at 300 °C and 600 °C and the cooling rate was 5 °C/min. After the cool down, the ampules were opened at ambient conditions.

BaHfO₃, SrHfO₃ were prepared by mixing of stoichiometric amount of BaCO₃ with HfO₂ and SrCO₃ with HfO₂, respectively, in an agate mortar with isopropyl alcohol. The precursors were grounded for 15 minutes, air dried and ground again for better homogeneity. The ground mixture was transferred into a ceramic boat, which was transferred into a furnace. The mixtures were heated with heat ramp rate of 10 °C/min to 1100 °C and held at this temperature for 16 hrs. The furnace was then allowed to cool down naturally. After the furnace reached the room temperature the samples were removed from the reaction boat and characterized.

In terms of boron content, the syntheses were investigated for the range of boron concentrations in the range $n = 2 - 3$ (see reactions (3) to (6) in the main text). In the reactions performed with $n = 2$ we found that in some cases the product contained various amounts of oxide contaminants. This was in all cases addressed by increasing the value of n to 2.2. Increasing the boron content past $n = 2.2$ did not lead to any observable improvement in the conversion rates or dynamics of reaction. However, since the unreacted excess boron is difficult to remove from the product mixture, in a typical reaction the boron content was kept at $n = 2.2$.

3. Product purification

The product removed from the reaction ampule was transferred into a beaker and sonicated for 10 min with a small amount (~20 ml) of HPLC grade methanol to remove any soluble byproducts (e.g. B₂O₃).

Figure S1. Auger spectra of a single grain of BaZrS₃ prepared by sulfurization of BaZrO₃ with boron sulfides at 1000 °C with $t = 36$ hrs., followed by washing of the sample with deionized water. The red trace shows the spectrum of the grain surface. The green trace shows the spectrum after surface sputtering of the grain for ~30 min. with 1000 eV Ar⁺ ion beam.

The sample was vacuum filtered using a Büchner funnel followed by drying in air for ~10 minutes. The dry sample was stored in a glass vial under ambient conditions for further characterization.

In several previous studies it was suggested that the side-products generated in the syntheses of CPs can be removed by washing of the synthesis product with deionized water. For samples prepared in this work we found that washing with deionized water led to an increase in the oxygen and decrease in sulfur content particularly at the CP grain surfaces as determined by Auger electron spectroscopy (see Fig. S1). More detailed analysis of this effect is currently in progress.

4. Characterization methods

4.1. X-ray diffraction

The crystalline phases present in the powder samples were identified using X-ray diffraction (XRD) (Panalytical Empyrean, Netherlands, Cu K α radiation). Rietveld analysis for quantitative analysis and lattice parameters determination was done using HighScore Plus on scans with 2θ ranging from 15° to 70° with a step of 0.026° .

4.2. Scanning Electron Microscopy

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were obtained on cold-pressed pellets using dual-beam scanning electron microscope combined with a high current focused ion beam (FIB) - FEI Quanta 3D 200i. SEM images of the surface morphology of the pellets were recorded at a magnification of 4000x.

4.3. Auger Electron Spectroscopy

Auger analysis was carried out in JEOL JAMP 9510-F field emission Auger microprobe (JEOL Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) at the energy of 10 keV, probe current of 10 nA, tilt angle of 30° and 65° take-off angle. Energy resolution used was 0.5% and Auger spectra were evaluated in derivative form. For grain bulk composition analysis, the powder grains were pre-sputtered with 1000 eV Ar $^+$ ions to eliminate the surface contamination.

5. ABO_3 sulfurization at 1000 °C

The metathesis of ternary oxides with boron sulfides at $T = 1000$ °C was investigated for $A = Sr^{2+}$, Ba^{2+} and $B = Zr^{4+}$, Hf^{4+} with the objective to prepare $BaZrS_3$, $BaHfS_3$, β - $SrZrS_3$, $SrHfS_3$. The reaction conditions, chemical composition of the product and other characteristics of the product are summarized in Table TS1. The XRD patterns of the products are shown in the main text as Fig. 1.

Table TS1. Summary of the reaction conditions and the product composition of the metathesis reaction of ABO_3 with boron and sulfur.

Starting material(s)	Heating program	Rxn mixture composition $ABO_3:B:S$	Product composition	Lattice parameters (exp.)	Lattice parameters (lit.)	Ref.
$BaZrO_3$	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 600 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 1000 °C, 36 hrs; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	1:2.2:3	$BaZrS_3$ (100%)	a = 7.064(2), b = 9.975(4), c = 7.029(2)	a = 7.0599(8), b = 9.9813(17), c = 7.0251(12)	(1)
$BaHfO_3$	As above	As above	$BaHfS_3$ (100%)	a = 7.030(5), b = 9.908(4), c = 7.009(4)	a = 7.002(6), b = 9.915(6), c = 6.995(6)	(1)
$SrZrO_3$	As above	As above	$SrZrS_3$ (100%)	a = 7.106(5), b = 9.763(7), c = 6.734(7)	a = 7.1085(4), b = 9.7661(5), c = 6.7350(3)	(1)
$SrHfO_3$	As above	As above	$SrHfS_3$ (100%)	a = 7.057(3), b = 9.723(7), c = 6.721(4)	a = 7.051(4), b = 9.716(4), c = 6.718(3)	(1)

6. BaZrO₃ sulfurization below 1000 °C

The conditions used in sulfurization of BaZrO₃ at moderate temperatures and chemical composition of the product are summarized in Table TS1. The XRD patterns of the products are shown in Fig. 2 of the main text. The detail of the same patterns in the region 26-35 2Theta (°), is shown in Fig. S2. Trace amounts of ZrO₂ byproduct in the sample prepared at 600°C can be identified in the figure.

Table TS2. Summary of the reaction conditions and the product composition of the metathesis reaction of ABO₃ with boron and sulfur.

Starting material(s)	Heating program	Total Rxn Time (hrs.)	Rxn mixture composition ABO ₃ :B:S	Product Composition
BaZrO ₃	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 500 °C, 48 hrs.; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	56.4	1:2.2:3	BaZrS ₃ (48.5%), BaZrO ₃ (31.0%), ZrS ₃ (20.5%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 500 °C, 168 hrs.; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	176.4	As above	BaZrS ₃ (63.8%), BaZrO ₃ (16.0%), ZrS ₃ (20.2%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 560 °C, 10 hrs.; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	18.6	As above	BaZrS ₃ (92.0%), BaZrO ₃ (8.0%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 560 °C, 48 hrs.; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	56.6	As above	BaZrS ₃ (95.0%), ZrO ₂ (5.0%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 560 °C, 96 hrs.; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	104.6	As above	BaZrS ₃ (97.7%), ZrO ₂ (2.3%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 600 °C, 5 hrs.; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	13.8	As above	BaZrS ₃ (97.0%), ZrO ₂ (3.0%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 600 °C, 10 hrs.; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	18.8	As above	BaZrS ₃ (92.0%), ZrO ₂ (8.0%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 600 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 1000 °C; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	16.5	As above	BaZrS₃ (100%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 600 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 900 °C; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	15.8	As above	BaZrS₃ (100%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 600 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 800 °C; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	15.2	As above	BaZrS ₃ (98.0%), ZrO ₂ (2.0%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 600 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 700 °C; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	14.5	As above	BaZrS ₃ (96.3%), ZrO ₂ (3.7%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 600 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 650 °C; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	14.2	As above	BaZrS ₃ (96.8%), ZrO ₂ (3.2%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 1000 °C; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	6.5	As above	BaZrS₃ (100%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 900 °C; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	5.8	As above	BaZrS₃ (100%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 800 °C; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	5.2	As above	BaZrS ₃ (99.5%), ZrO ₂ (0.5%)
As above	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 700 °C; cool down 5 °C/min; RT	4.5	As above	BaZrS ₃ (92.9%), ZrO ₂ (7.1%)

Figure S2. Detail of the XRD patterns from Fig. 2 of the main text in the region 26-35 2Theta (°), showing contributions of BaZrS₃, BaZrO₃ and various reaction side products to the signal of the product mixtures.

7. $A_xO_y + BO_2$ sulfurization

The metathesis of binary oxides with boron sulfides was investigated for $A = \text{Eu}^{2+}$ and Sr^{2+} and $B = \text{Zr}^{4+}$, Hf^{4+} , with the objective to prepare EuHfS_3 and $\beta\text{-SrZrS}_3$. The reaction conditions, chemical composition of the product and other characteristics of the product are summarized in Table TS3. The XRD patterns of the products are shown in Fig. S3.

Table TS3. Summary of the reaction conditions and the product composition of the metathesis reaction of $A_xO_y + BO_2$ with boron and sulfur.

Starting material(s)	Heating program	Rxn mixture composition $A_xO_y : BO_2 : B:S$	Product composition	Lattice parameters (exp.)	Lattice parameters (lit.)	Ref.
$^a\text{SrO}, \text{ZrO}_2$	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 600 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 1000 °C, 36 hrs; cool off 5 °C/min; RT	1:1:2.2:3	$\beta\text{-SrZrS}_3$ (98.9%), ZrO_2 (1.1%)	a = 7.109(5), b = 9.77(2), c = 6.735(5)	a = 7.1085(4), b = 9.7661(5), c = 6.7350(3)	(1)
$\text{Eu}_2\text{O}_3, \text{HfO}_2$	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5 hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 600 °C, 5hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 1100 °C, 168 hrs; cool off 5 °C/min; RT	1:2:4.4:6	EuHfS_3 (95.2%) HfO_2 (4.8%)	a = 7.064(8), b = 9.68(1), c = 6.656(8)	a = 7.057(3), b = 9.678(4), c = 6.661(3)	(1)

^aReaction mixture prepared in the glovebox and sealed without exposure of the mixture to air.

Figure S3. Powder x-ray diffraction patterns (blue) of the products of the reaction of the binary oxides and boron sulfides. The reference literature patterns for the corresponding ternary sulfides and identified contaminants are shown in orange.

8. A + BO₂ sulfurization

The reaction of elements with binary oxides was investigated for A = Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺ and B = Zr⁴⁺ with aim to prepare BaZrS₃ and β-SrZrS₃. The reaction conditions, chemical composition of the product and other characteristics of the product are summarized in Table TS4. The XRD patterns of the products are shown in Fig. S4.

Table TS4. Summary of the reaction conditions and the product composition of the metathesis reaction of A + BO₂ with boron and sulfur.

Starting material(s)	Heating program	Rxn mixture composition A:BO ₂ :B:S	Product composition	Lattice parameters (exp.)	Lattice parameters (lit.)	Ref.
^a Ba, ZrO ₂	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 600 °C, 5hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 1000 °C, 36 hrs; cool off 5 °C/min; RT	1:1:1.46:3	BaZrS ₃ (27.6%) Ba ₃ Zr ₂ S ₇ (56.7%) ZrOS (15.7%)	b	a = 7.0599(8), b = 9.9813(17), c = 7.0251(12)	(1)
^a Sr, ZrO ₂	As above	As above	β-SrZrS ₃ (74%) ZrO ₂ (8%) ZrS ₂ (18%)	a = 7.108(9), b = 9.77(2), c = 6.739(8)	a = 7.1085(4), b = 9.7661(5), c = 6.7350(3)	(1)

^aReaction mixture prepared in the glovebox and sealed without exposure of the mixture to air,

^bLattice parameters were not calculated due to the low amount of the BaZrS₃ in the product.

Figure S4. Powder x-ray diffraction patterns (blue) of the products of the reaction of the elements with binary oxides and boron sulphides. The reference literature patterns for the corresponding ternary sulphides and identified contaminants are shown in orange.

9. $ACO_3 + BO_2$ sulfurization

The reaction of carbonates with binary oxides was investigated for $A = Ba^{2+}$ and Sr^{2+} and $B = Zr^{4+}$, Hf^{4+} with the aim to prepare $BaZrS_3$, β - $SrZrS_3$, $BaHfS_3$, $SrHfS_3$. The reaction conditions, chemical composition of the product and other characteristics of the product are summarized in Table TS5. The XRD patterns of the products are shown in Fig. S5.

Table TS5. Summary of the reaction conditions and the product composition of the metathesis reaction of $ACO_3 + BO_2$ with boron and sulfur.

Starting material(s)	Heating program	Rxn mixture composition $ACO_3:BO_2:B:S$	Product composition	Lattice parameters (exp.)	Lattice parameters (lit.)	Ref.
$BaCO_3, ZrO_2$	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 600 °C, 5hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 1000 °C, 36 hrs; cool off 5 °C/min; RT	1:1:2.2:3.	$BaZrS_3 + ZrO_2$ + unidentified reflections	a = 7.059(9), b = 9.98(1), c = 7.00 (1)	a = 7.0599(8), b = 9.9813(17), c = 7.0251(12)	(1)
$BaCO_3, HfO_2$	As above	As above	$BaHfS_3 + HfO_2$ + unidentified reflections	a = 7.09(1), b = 9.92(1), c = 6.989(8)	a = 7.002(6), b = 9.915(6), c = 6.995(6)	(1)
$SrCO_3, ZrO_2$	As above	As above	β - $SrZrS_3$ (82.1%) ZrO_2 (17.9%)	a = 7.109(3), b = 9.758(5), c = 6.738(3)	a = 7.1085(4), b = 9.7661(5), c = 6.7350(3)	(1)
$SrCO_3, HfO_2$	As above	As above	$SrHfS_3$ (70.8%) HfO_2 (29.2%)	a = 7.057(4), b = 9.722(6), c = 6.725(5)	a = 7.051(4), b = 9.716(4), c = 6.718(3)	(1)

Figure S5. Powder x-ray diffraction patterns (blue) of the products of the reaction of the carbonates, binary oxides and boron sulfides. The reference literature patterns for the corresponding ternary sulfides and identified contaminants are shown in orange.

10. Sulfurization of partially oxidized binary sulfides

The metathesis of partially oxidized binary sulfides with boron was investigated for the preparation of pure ZrS_2 , BaS and SrS . The starting materials were commercially available ZrS_2 , BaS , and SrS , as obtained from the vendor. The reaction conditions, chemical composition of the product and other characteristics of the starting materials and the products are summarized in Table TS6. The XRD patterns of the products are shown in Fig. S6.

Table TS6. Summary of the reaction conditions and the product composition of the metathesis reaction of oxidized binary sulfides with boron and sulfur.

Starting material(s)	Heating program	Rxn mixture composition $AS_2:B:S$	Product composition
ZrS_2 (75%), $ZrOS$ (25%)	RT; ramp 5 °C/min; 300 °C, 5hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 600 °C, 5hrs.; ramp 5 °C/min; 950 °C, 48 hrs; cool off 5 °C/min; RT	1:2.2:1.5	ZrS_2 (100%)
BaS (80%), $BaSO_x$ - $Ba_x(SO_3)_y \cdot nH_2O$ (20%)	As above	1:2.66:1	BaS (100%)
SrS (55%), $SrCO_3$ (15%), $SrSO_4$ (30%)	As above	1:3.32:1	SrS (100%)

Figure S6. Powder x-ray diffraction patterns of (a) partially oxidized binary sulphides upon receiving from a vendor and (b) after heating in the presence of boron for 48 hrs. at temperature 950 °C. The XRD patterns of the measured compounds are shown in blue. The reference literature patterns for the corresponding binary sulphides and identified contaminants are shown in orange.

11. SEM of BaZrO₃ and BaZrS₃.

Figure S7. SEM images of the BaZrO₃ grains before sulfurization (a) and the BaZrS₃ CP grain after sulfurization (b).

12. Heats of reactions for relevant chemical processes

In this section we summarize the heats of reaction relevant for the process discussed in the main text and in the supporting information. The heats of reaction were calculated from experimental heats of formation for the relevant compounds summarized in ref. 2. Where experimental data were not available, we used the heats of formation available at the materialsproject.org,³ calculated by the Density Functional Theory.

Table TS7. Calculated heats of reactions for selected chemical processes at 298 K.

No.	Reaction	$\Delta H_{rxn, 298\text{ K}}$ (kJ/mol)
1	$\text{Ba} + \text{ZrO}_2 + 1.33\text{B} + 3\text{S} \rightarrow \text{BaZrS}_3 + 0.67\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$	-809.3
2	$\text{Sr} + \text{ZrO}_2 + 1.33\text{B} + 3\text{S} \rightarrow \text{SrZrS}_3 + 0.67\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$	-800.5
3	$\text{SrO} + \text{ZrO}_2 + 2\text{B} + 3\text{S} \rightarrow \text{SrZrS}_3 + \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$	-628.1
4	$0.5\text{Eu}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{HfO}_2 + 2.3\text{B} + 3\text{S} \rightarrow \text{EuHfS}_3 + 1.16\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$	-601.9
5	$\text{BaZrO}_3 + 2\text{B} + 3\text{S} \rightarrow \text{BaZrS}_3 + \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$	-554.3
6	$\text{SrZrO}_3 + 2\text{B} + 3\text{S} \rightarrow \text{SrZrS}_3 + \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$	-553.5
7	$\text{EuHfO}_3 + 2\text{B} + 3\text{S} \rightarrow \text{EuHfS}_3 + \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$	-536.8
8	$\text{BaHfO}_3 + 2\text{B} + 3\text{S} \rightarrow \text{BaHfS}_3 + \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$	-517.5
9	$\text{SrHfO}_3 + 2\text{B} + 3\text{S} \rightarrow \text{SrHfS}_3 + \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$	-492.3
10	$\text{BaCO}_3 + \text{ZrO}_2 + 2\text{B} + 3\text{S} \rightarrow \text{BaZrS}_3 + \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$	-410.5
11	$\text{SrCO}_3 + \text{ZrO}_2 + 2\text{B} + 3\text{S} \rightarrow \text{SrZrS}_3 + \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$	-393.9
12	$\text{BaCO}_3 + \text{HfO}_2 + 2\text{B} + 3\text{S} \rightarrow \text{BaHfS}_3 + \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$	-382.2
13	$\text{SrCO}_3 + \text{HfO}_2 + 2\text{B} + 3\text{S} \rightarrow \text{SrHfS}_3 + \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$	-365.2
14	$\text{BaO} + \text{ZrO}_2 + 1.5\text{CS}_2 \rightarrow \text{BaZrS}_3 + 1.5\text{CO}_2$	-173.4
15	$\text{BaO} + \text{ZrO}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{S} \rightarrow \text{BaZrS}_3 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	-71.7
16	$\text{BaZrO}_3 + 1.5\text{CS}_2 \rightarrow \text{BaZrS}_3 + 1.5\text{CO}_2$	-47.9
17	$\text{BaS} + \text{ZrS}_2 \rightarrow \text{BaZrS}_3$	-35.7
18	$\text{BaZrO}_3 + 3\text{H}_2\text{S} \rightarrow \text{BaZrS}_3 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	53.7
19	$\text{BaCO}_3 + \text{ZrO}_2 + 1.5\text{CS}_2 \rightarrow \text{BaZrS}_3 + 2.5\text{CO}_2$	95.9
20	$\text{BaCO}_3 + \text{ZrO}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{S} \rightarrow \text{BaZrS}_3 + \text{CO}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	197.6

13. References

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